

EYLER TEOREMASINING TURLI ISBOTLARI

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Annotatsiya: Uchburchaklarga ichki va tashqi chizilgan aylanalarning markazlari orasidagi masofani hisoblash formulasi ya'ni Eyley teoremasining turli xil isbotlarini keltiramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Eyley teoremasi, markaz, radius, vektor , trigonometriya , bissektrisa , kollinear

Teorema (Eyley). Agar ABC uchburchakka ichki va tashqi chizilgan aylanalarning radiuslari r, R bo'lsa, ularning markazlari orasidagi masofa d uchun

$$d^2 = R^2 - 2Rr$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi.

1-isboti: [2] kitobda keltirilgan isbotni keltiramiz. ABC uchburchak o'tmas

burchakli ($\angle C = \gamma > 90^\circ$) deb hisoblaymiz. Bu holda tashqi chizilgan aylana markazi uchburchakdan tashqarida bo'ladi. $AB = c, BC = a, CA = b$ va ichki chizilgan aylana markazi O_1 , tashqi chizilgan aylana markazi O_2 bo'lsin. Ichki chizilgan aylana AB tomonga K nuqtada urinsin. O_1K ning davomiga perpendikulyar bo'lgan O_2M kesmani va $O_2P \perp AB$ kesmani o'tkazamiz O_1MO_2 uchburchakda

$O_1M = r + \sqrt{R^2 - \left(\frac{c}{2}\right)^2}$, $O_2M = PK = \frac{|a-b|}{2}$, $O_1O_2 = d$ bo'lgani uchun

$$d^2 = \left(r + \sqrt{R^2 - \left(\frac{c}{2}\right)^2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{a-b}{2} \right)^2 = R^2 - 2Rr \cos \gamma - (p-a)(p-b) + r^2.$$

Endi ba'zi shakl almashtirishlarni bajaramiz:

1. $\cos \gamma = \frac{a^2+b^2-c^2}{2ab} = \frac{(a-b)^2-c^2+2ab}{2ab} = -\frac{2(p-a)(p-b)}{ab} + 1$;
2. $\frac{Rr(p-a)(p-b)}{ab} = \frac{\frac{abc}{4} \cdot \frac{S_{\Delta ABC}(p-a)(p-b)}{p}}{ab} = \frac{c(p-a)(p-b)}{4p}$;
3. $r^2 = \left(\frac{S_{\Delta ABC}}{p}\right)^2 = \frac{(p-a)(p-b)(p-c)}{p} = (p-a)(p-b) - c \frac{(p-a)(p-b)}{p}$.

$$\text{Bularga ko'ra } d^2 = R^2 - 2Rr \left(-\frac{2(p-a)(p-b)}{ab} + 1 \right) - \frac{c(p-a)(p-b)}{p} = R^2 - 2Rr + 4 \cdot \frac{Rr(p-a)(p-b)}{ab} - \frac{c(p-a)(p-b)}{p} = R^2 - 2Rr + 4 \cdot \frac{c(p-a)(p-b)}{4p} - \frac{c(p-a)(p-b)}{p} = R^2 - 2Rr.$$

Demak, formula isbotlandi.

2-isboti: [1] kitobda keltirilgan isbotni keltiramiz. Trigonometriyadan foydalanib isbotlaymiz.

Belgilash kiritamiz: $O_1O_2 = d$, $AO_2 = R$, $O_1P = r$, $\angle A = \alpha$, $\angle B = \beta$, $\angle C = \gamma$, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 180^\circ$, $\frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} = 90^\circ - \frac{\gamma}{2}$, $p = \frac{a+b+c}{2}$. Bizga ma'lumki, uchburchakka ichki chizilgan aylananing markazi bissektrisalar kesishish nuqtasida, unga tashqi chizilgan aylana markazi esa tomonlariga o'tkazilgan o'rta perpendikulyar kesishish nuqtasida yotadi. Shularga

asosan:

$$AO_1 = \frac{r}{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2}}, \angle PAO_1 = \frac{\alpha}{2}, \angle AO_2Q = \beta, \angle QAO_2 = 90^\circ - \beta \Rightarrow \angle O_1AO_2 = \beta + \frac{\alpha}{2} - 90^\circ$$

tengliklarni olamiz. Quyidagi formulalarni ko'rib o'taylik:

$$\frac{\alpha}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{b}{\sin \beta} = \frac{c}{\sin \gamma} = 2R \quad (1)$$

$$r = \frac{S}{p} \quad (2)$$

(1) formulani (2) formulaga asosan quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$r = \frac{S}{p} = \frac{ab \sin \gamma}{a + b + c} = \frac{4R^2 \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma}{2R(\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma)} = \frac{2R \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma}{\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma} \quad (3)$$

Endi AO_1O_2 uchburchakda kosinuslar teoremasini qo'llab, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$d^2 = \frac{r^2}{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} + R^2 - \frac{2Rr}{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot \cos \left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2} - 90^\circ \right) = R^2 + \frac{r \cdot r}{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{2Rr}{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot \sin \left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)$$

(3) formulaga asosan

$$d^2 = R^2 + \frac{r}{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot \frac{2R \sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma}{\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma} - \frac{2Rr}{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2}} \cdot \sin \left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) = R^2 - 2Rr \left(\frac{\sin \left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)}{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{\sin \alpha \sin \beta \sin \gamma}{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} (\sin \alpha + \sin \beta + \sin \gamma)} \right).$$

Bu tenglikdagi qavs ichidagi ifodani 1 ga tengligini ko'rsatish kifoya.

$$\frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{\sin\alpha \sin\beta \sin\gamma}{\sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}(\sin\alpha+\sin\beta+\sin\gamma)} = \frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{2\cos\frac{\alpha}{2}\sin\beta\sin\gamma}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}\left(\sin\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\alpha-\beta}{2}+\sin\gamma\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{4\cos\frac{\alpha}{2}\sin\beta\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}\left(2\sin\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\alpha-\beta}{2}+2\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{2\cos\frac{\alpha}{2}\sin\beta\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}\left(\cos\frac{\alpha-\beta}{2}+\cos\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right)} = \frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{4\cos\frac{\alpha}{2}\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{2\cos\frac{\alpha}{2}\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}} = \frac{\sin\left(\beta+\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\sin\left(90^\circ-\frac{\gamma}{2}+\frac{\beta}{2}\right)-2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{\gamma}{2}-\frac{\beta}{2}\right)-2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}+\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}-2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\cos\frac{\beta+\gamma}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}}{\sin\frac{\alpha}{2}} = 1.$$

Demak 1 ga tengligi ko'rsatildi.

3-isboti: [1] kitobda keltirilgan isbotni keltiramiz. Vektorlar yordamida isbotlaymiz.

Bizga ma'lumki, uchburchakka ichki chizilgan aylananing markazi burchak bissektrissalari kesishgan nuqtasi bo'ladi va I (markazi) harfi bilan belgilanadi.

Ushbu $\vec{CB} = \vec{a}$, $\vec{CA} = \vec{b}$,
 $|CA| = a$, $|CA| = b$, $|AB| = c$

belgilashlarni kiritib olamiz. $\vec{CI}$ vektor ham, $b \cdot \vec{a} + a \cdot \vec{b}$ vektor ham ACB burchak bissektrissasi bo'yicha yo'nalganligi uchun ular o'zaro kollinear. Chunki $a \cdot \vec{b} = b \cdot \vec{a}$, bundan $CKEF$ romb ekanligi kelib chiqadi. $\vec{CE}$ rombning diagonal bo'lgani uchun burchak bissektrissasi bo'ladi. Bundan

$$\vec{CI} = \lambda(b \cdot \vec{a} + a \cdot \vec{b})$$

bo'ladi. Bunga ko'ra $\vec{AI} = \vec{AC} + \vec{CI} = \lambda b \cdot \vec{a} + (\lambda \vec{a} - 1) \cdot \vec{b}$. Xuddi shunday $\vec{AI}$ vektor ham, $c \cdot \vec{AC} + b \cdot \vec{AB}$ vektor ham BAC burchak bissektrissasi bo'yicha yo'nalgan. Chunki $c \cdot \vec{b} = b \cdot \vec{c}$, bundan $AGMN$ romb ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Shunga ko'ra

$$\vec{AI} = \mu(c \cdot \vec{AC} + b \cdot \vec{AB}) = \mu b \vec{a} - (\mu b + \mu c) \cdot \vec{b}$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. $\vec{AI}$ uchun olingan ikkita tenglikni bir-biridan ayirsak, ushbu

$$(\lambda - \mu)b \vec{a} - (\lambda a - \mu b + \mu c - 1)\vec{b} = 0$$

tenlik hosil bo'ladi. Bu yerda $\vec{a}$ va $\vec{b}$ vektorlar kollinear emasligini hisobga olsak, $\lambda = \mu$ va $\lambda a + \mu b + \mu c = 1$ tenglikni olamiz. Bundan ushbu

$$\vec{CI} = \frac{1}{a+b+c} \cdot (b \vec{a} + a \vec{b})$$

tenglik hosil bo'ladi.

Agar A_1 orqali BC tomonning o'rtasini va B_1 orqali AC tomonning o'rtasini belgilasak, u holda $\vec{CO} + \vec{OA}_1 = \frac{1}{2}\vec{a}$ va $\vec{CO} + \vec{OB}_1 = \frac{1}{2}\vec{b}$ tenglikni mos ravishda $\vec{a}$ va $\vec{b}$ vektorlarga ko'paytirib, ushbu

$$\vec{CO} \cdot \vec{a} = \frac{1}{2}a^2 \text{ va } \vec{CO} \cdot \vec{b} = \frac{1}{2}b^2 \quad (1)$$

tengliklarni olamiz. Chunki $\vec{OA}_1 \perp \vec{a}$ va $\vec{OB}_1 \perp \vec{b}$. Bundan $\vec{OA}_1 \cdot \vec{a} = 0$ va $\vec{OB}_1 \cdot \vec{b} = 0$.

Endi ushbu

$$\vec{OI} = \vec{CI} - \vec{CO} = \frac{1}{a+b+c} \cdot (b \cdot \vec{a} + a \cdot \vec{b}) - \vec{CO}$$

tenglikning kvadratini (1) formulalardan foydalanib hisoblaymiz:

$$\vec{OI}^2 = \frac{1}{(a+b+c)^2} (b \cdot \vec{a} + a \cdot \vec{b})^2 - \frac{2}{a+b+c} (b \cdot \vec{a} + a \cdot \vec{b}) \cdot \vec{CO} + R^2 = \frac{2a^2b^2(1+\cos\gamma)}{(a+b+c)^2} - \frac{ab(a+b)}{a+b+c} + R^2$$

Bu yerda ushbu

$$1 + \cos\gamma = 1 + \frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab} = \frac{(a+b+c)(a+b-c)}{2ab}$$

tenglikdan foydalansak,

$$\vec{OI}^2 = R^2 - \frac{abc}{a+b+c} = R^2 - 2 \cdot \frac{abc}{4S} \cdot \frac{2S}{a+b+c} = R^2 - 2Rr$$

Eyler formulasi kelib chiqadi.

4-isboti: [1] kitobda keltirilgan isbotni keltiramiz. Quyidagicha belgilashlar kiritamiz.

$$ON = d, OL = OM = R, NT = r$$

BQ va AK - bissektrissalar. $\angle CBQ = \angle CAQ$ chunki $\vec{CQ}$ yoyga tiralgan. Bundan $\triangle ANQ$ teng yonli $AQ = NQ$.

Sababi $\triangle ABN$ da bitta $\angle ANQ$ tashqi burchak $\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}$ ga teng.

$$\begin{cases} LN = OL + ON = R + d \\ MN = OM - ON = R - d \end{cases}$$

Bu tengliklarni hadma-had ko'paytirib

$$LN \cdot MN = R^2 - d^2$$

Tenglikni olamiz. Vatarlar haqidagi teorema ko'ra

$$BN \cdot NQ = LN \cdot MN = R^2 - d^2 \Rightarrow BN \cdot NQ = R^2 - d^2$$

Yuqoridagi $AQ = NQ$ tenglikni e'tiborga olib

$$BN \cdot NQ = BN \cdot AQ = R^2 - d^2 \Rightarrow AQ \cdot BN = R^2 - d^2 \quad (1)$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. $\triangle TBN \sim \triangle ASQ$ chunki $\angle ABQ = \angle ASQ$ bitta yoyga tiralgan ichki burchak. $\angle CAQ = \angle BTN$, sababi $\angle SAQ$ diametrga tiralgan ichki burchak.

Bu tengliklardan quyidagilarni yozamiz:

$$\frac{r}{AQ} = \frac{BN}{2R} \Rightarrow AQ \cdot BN = 2Rr \quad (2)$$

Hosil bolgan (2) va (1) tengliklardan

$$\begin{cases} AQ \cdot BN = R^2 - d^2 \\ AQ \cdot BN = 2Rr \end{cases} \Rightarrow d^2 = R^2 - 2Rr$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Shu bilan Eyler teoremasining bir qancha isbotlarini ko'rib chiqdik.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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